

DIRECT EVALUATION OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN A CARBON FIBER

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SUMMARY

For the direct measurement of the fracture toughness of the carbon fiber, a new technique was proposed and examined its applicability. At first, machining condition of the notch was examined. The notch was introduced using focused ion beam (FIB). The ion beam can be electronically scanned to introduce a sharp notch on the carbon fiber. Notches with various notch width and length were introduced by changing beam and scanning conditions. Tensile tests on notched carbon fibers were carried out following the test method for carbon fiber monofilaments. Fractured specimens were successfully corrected without secondary damage using protection films. SEM observations revealed that a crack propagated from a notch-tip, and notch size was able to be determined successfully. Effect of notch root radius was also examined to investigate the validity of the fracture toughness obtained by this method.

Keywords: Carbon fiber, Focused ion beam, Finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Fracture toughness of carbon fiber is of great interest as well as its strength, because it is essentially important when fracture behavior of composites was investigated. For example, fracture mode of brittle matrix composites are strongly affected by the fiber fracture toughness as well as its interface toughness [1]. The measurement of fiber fracture toughness is, however, thought to be difficult due to its small diameter. One of the practical ways to estimate fracture toughness is determination of the initial crack size by observing fracture mirror size on a tensile fracture surface of un-notched specimens [2]. Since the mirror size measurement involves a considerable error, estimated fracture toughness is usually scattered significantly. Accuracy of the measured fracture toughness will be significantly improved, if a notch is introduced intentionally by controlling its size and shape. In this study, therefore, a new measurement technique was proposed to estimate fracture toughness of the carbon fiber.

At first, applicability of the focused ion beam (FIB) system was examined as a machining tool of notches. The FIB is regarded as a useful machining tool to prepare samples for transmission electron microscope observations. Recent FIB systems have less than 10 nm beam diameter, achieving micro-machining by scanning the beam electronically. Various sizes and types of notches were tried to be introduced on the

carbon fibers. Tensile tests were carried out on the notched carbon fibers to examine the validity of this technique.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimens Preparation

The carbon fiber tested in this experiment is a PAN based high strength type carbon fiber (IM-600; 6000 filaments) manufactured by Toho Tenax Co. Ltd, Japan. A carbon monofilament was extracted from a bundle, and was attached on a holder as shown in Figure 1. An aluminum holder and carbon tapes were used since electrical conductivity was required to introduce a notch by the FIB.

The notch was introduced using the FIB system (JFIB-2300; JEOL Co. Ltd., Japan) on a carbon fiber. Ga^+ ion beam was extracted from an ion source and accelerated with 30kV accelerating voltage. Various types of notches were introduced by changing a beam diameter and other machining conditions. Details of the conditions were shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of fixture

Table 1: FIB machining conditions

Acceleration Voltage	30 kV
Extraction Voltage	5.58 kV
Emission Current	1.26 μA
Ion Beam Current	0.6 μA
Filament Current	1.62 A
Filament Voltage	0.58 V
Probe Current	1 pA
Beam Diameter	7 ~ 18 nm

Fracture Toughness Test

Figure 2 schematically shows a cross section of the carbon fiber on a notched plane. A notch was introduced by the FIB system on one side surface of the carbon fiber with various notch depths (a) as indicated by gray area in Fig.2. Notched carbon fibers were tested in tension with crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min. following the tensile test method of carbon fiber monofilaments. Plastic films were set on both sides of a carbon fiber specimen, and liquid detergent was filled between them to avoid secondary damage of the carbon fiber. After tensile tests, liquid detergent was removed by dipping in water. Fracture surface was observed by SEM to confirm a fracture position and to determine the notch length, a .

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of notched carbon fiber

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

Determination of Fracture Toughness

Energy release rate, G_I , at the center of the crack front was examined by the finite elements method using the virtual crack closure method (VCCM). Figure 2 shows the model of a carbon monofilament which has a straight edge crack from the surface located at its center. The model was analyzed as both isotropic and orthotropic materials. In the case of the isotropic material, Young's modulus (E) is set to be 285GPa, Poison's ratio (ν) 0.3. Table 2 shows the material properties used for the analysis in the case of the orthotropic material. In the case of isotropic material, the energy release rate (G_I) is converted to the stress intensity factor (K_I) by the following equation

$$G_I = \frac{K_I^2(1-\nu^2)}{E} \quad (1)$$

where assumption of plain strain condition in the neighborhood of the crack front is made. In the case of orthotropic material, following equation is used [3].

$$G_I = K_I^2 \sqrt{\frac{a_{11}a_{22}}{2}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}} + \frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where

$$a_{11} = \frac{1}{E_{11}}, \quad a_{22} = \frac{1}{E_{22}}, \quad a_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}}, \quad a_{12} = a_{21} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} = -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} \quad (3)$$

Table 2: Material properties used for orthotropic analysis

Young's modulus [GPa]	Poisson's Ratio	Shear modulus [GPa]
E_{11} 285	ν_{12} 0.300	G_{12} 20.0
E_{22} 30.0	ν_{23} 0.400	G_{23} 10.7
E_{22} 30.0	ν_{31} 0.0316	G_{31} 20.0

The dimensionless stress intensity factor is described by

$$f = \frac{K_I}{\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}} \quad (4)$$

where σ is the far field stress and a is the crack length. Figure 3 shows the comparison between f calculated by equation (1) (isotropic case) and that in [4]. A good agreement is obtained which implies the accuracy of the present calculation. Figure 4 shows the comparison of f between isotropic and orthotropic cases. The dimensionless stress intensity factor is approximated as

$$f = \frac{K_I}{\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}} = 17.2\left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^3 - 5.81\left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^2 + 1.73\left(\frac{a}{D}\right) + 0.886 \quad (5)$$

in the isotropic case and as

$$f = \frac{K_I}{\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}} = 9.19\left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^3 - 2.87\left(\frac{a}{D}\right)^2 + 0.859\left(\frac{a}{D}\right) + 0.511 \quad (6)$$

in the orthotropic case. Fracture toughness was calculated by these approximations.

Figure 3: Comparison of the dimensionless stress intensity factor (isotropic)

Figure 4: Comparison of the dimensionless stress intensity factors between isotropic and orthotropic cases

Stress Analysis of a Notched Carbon Fiber

Fracture toughness of a carbon fiber was evaluated assuming that the notches on the carbon fibers can be considered as cracks. Therefore it is important to analyze stresses in a notched carbon fiber and to evaluate the strength of fibers in addition to calculating fracture toughness. In this section, stress concentration factor at the notch root in the carbon fibers were considered.

Figure 5 shows an analytical model. This is the cross-section and half model of a carbon fiber. The maximum stress in x_1 (fiber axis) direction (σ_{max}) near the notch-tip was calculated through FEM analyses.

Figure 5: Analytical model

Fiber width (D) was $5\mu\text{m}$, notch length (a) was $1.0\mu\text{m}$, and notch-tip width (w) was set to be 0.05 , 0.1 , 0.15 , 0.2 , 0.3 , 0.4 and $0.5\mu\text{m}$. Tensile stress (σ_t) of 100MPa in x_1 direction was applied at upper end of the model. On each model three kinds of analyses were conducted by changing the number of element coarse, intermediate, and fine. The FEM analyses were carried out as a plane strain condition using orthotropic material properties in Table 2. The analyses stress concentration factor (α) was defined by

$$\alpha = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_t} \quad (7)$$

Figure 6 shows the stress concentration factor as a function of notch-tip width. It is seen that stress concentration factor increases as the notch-tip width (w) becomes smaller and that it is influenced by the element size, or the number of elements. This influence was larger as the notch-tip width (w) was smaller. Especially stress concentration factor increased as the element size was smaller.

Figure 6: Stress concentration factor at the notch root

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Notch Machining

Figure 7 shows typical outlooks of notched carbon fibers introduced with different beam condition. When the beam diameter of 7nm was used, a sharp notch was successfully introduced with notch-tip width of less than 50 nm as shown in Fig.7(a). On the other hand, 360nm notch-tip width was obtained by changing a beam diameter (18 nm) and scan area as shown in Fig.7(b). Various kinds of notches were introduced with different notch-width and notch-length.

Figure 7: Typical outlooks of notched carbon fibers
 (a) introduced by the beam with 7 nm diameter,
 (b) by the beam with 18 nm diameter

2. Tensile Test

A typical load-displacement (P - δ) curve was shown in Figure 8. The P - δ curve was linear up to the final fracture. In all tests, same behavior was observed. After tensile tests, specimens were successfully corrected without secondary damage and fracture surface could be observed as shown in Figure 9. A flat notch surface was clearly observed as indicated by a circle on the fracture surface. It was also observed that the notch front was straight, indicating machining by the FIB was applicable to the notch introduction. Notch length, a , was measured from the micrograph for every specimen. On the fracture surface, hackle pattern was clearly observed from the notch tip.

Figure 8: Typical load-displacement curve of notched carbon fiber in tension test

Figure 9: Typical fracture surface of notched carbon fiber tested in tension.

This means that the fracture of the notched carbon fiber originated from a notch-tip. It was confirmed with these observations that fracture toughness tests were successfully carried out with the present technique.

Based on the fracture toughness tests with various widths of notches, effect of notch width was examined as shown in Figure 10. Although K_{IC} was somewhat scattered, it showed almost constant value of $1.6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (isotropic) and $1.0 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (orthotropic) on average, when the notch-tip width was less than $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. Since the fracture toughness of the PAN based carbon fibers were reported to be in the range from $1\sim 2 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ [2], present results is expected to give the reasonable value in this range of notch width. On the other hand, K_{IC} linearly increased with notch-tip width, if the notch-tip width was more than $0.2 \mu\text{m}$. These results suggest that the fracture toughness tests should be carried out with small enough notch-tip width to which calculated fracture toughness is insensitive.

Figure 10: Fracture toughness of a carbon fiber

Strength evaluation of a notched carbon fiber

The values of K_{IC} in Fig.10 were calculated by equation (4) using the experimental values for σ and the result of FEM analyses for f . In fact fracture toughness of a carbon fiber was evaluated assuming that the notches on the carbon fibers can be considered as cracks. Therefore it is important to analyze stresses in a notched carbon fiber and to evaluate the strength in the fiber in addition to calculating fracture toughness. The strength in the carbon fiber was evaluated with the result of stress concentration factor at the notch root.

It was assumed the fibers fail when the maximum stress at the notch root reaches the fiber tensile strength. The fracture stress (σ_0) can be calculated by

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{\sigma_f}{\alpha} \quad (8)$$

where σ_f is the tensile strength which is set to be 6GPa in the present study. Figure 11 shows the calculated fracture stress using equation (8). Comparison with the experimental results is shown in the Figure.

Figure 11 shows that the calculated fracture stress (σ_0) was much smaller than those of experiments and that both calculated and experimentally-obtained fracture stresses increased as the notch-tip width (w) was larger. It was also found that the slope of analytical values was smaller than that of experimental values.

The calculated fracture stress was much smaller than that by experiments. The discrepancy may be due to the value of tensile strength of the carbon fiber. In the present study, the tensile strength was assumed to be 6GPa. The gage length of a carbon fiber in these analyses was in the micron-order, where internal defects are fewer than in millimeter-order. Therefore it is possible to estimate larger tensile strength. Orowan proposed an expression to show that ideal strength (σ_{ideal}) is nearly equal to one tenth of Young's modulus (E)

Figure 11: Fracture stress (comparison between analyses and experimental results)

Figure 12: Discussion on tensile strength

$$\sigma_{ideal} \approx E \times \frac{1}{10} \quad (9)$$

Young's modulus of the carbon fiber in fiber axial direction is 285GPa. Therefore it is possible to estimate that the ideal strength of the carbon fiber is 24 to 30GPa. Figure 12 shows that calculated and experimental fracture stresses show better agreement if the tensile strength of 24 to 30GPa based on Orowan's equation (9) were used.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Various types of notches with straight notch front could be successfully introduced on carbon fiber monofilaments using a focused ion beam machining system.
- (2) Fracture surface observation revealed that fracture of notched carbon fibers originated from notch tip with hackle pattern, indicating present technique is applicable for fracture toughness tests of the carbon fiber.
- (3) Effect of notch tip width was clearly shown that the fracture toughness tests should be carried out with small enough notch tip width to which calculated fracture toughness is insensitive.
- (4) Stress intensity factor is calculated by using the VCCM technique as a function of crack length for both isotropic and orthotropic carbon fibers. The fracture toughness of IM600 was estimated as $1.6 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (isotropic), $1.0 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (orthotropic) on average.

- (5) Through analyzing stress and evaluating strength of the carbon fiber both calculated and experimentally-obtained fracture stresses increased as the notch-tip width was wider, however analytical values were much smaller than experimental values. The difference between analytical and experimental values may come from the value of tensile strength of the carbon fiber. If the tensile strength was set to be 24 to 30GPa based on Orowan's equation, the calculated and experimental fracture stresses show better agreement.

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